

Weighted Z-method for meta-analysis of genome-wide association studies

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1 Introduction

Individual-level data from Genome-wide studies (GWAS) are often not available, and their analysis is also computationally intensive. For these reasons, meta-analysis methods based solely on summary statistics have been developed and tested, and it has been proven that they are as effective as pooling raw data from different studies (1). I show in this brief document the theoretical background to the application of the weighted Z-method to GWAS meta-analysis, and I apply it to two simulated GWASs with no overlap in subjects, generated by a custom R script. At the end, I introduce a possible approach to the meta analysis of GWASs with overlapping samples.

2 Origin of the Z-transform test

Consider a scenario in which all we have are the p-values from a set of k studies, where we test the same null hypothesis. We wonder how to perform a meta-analysis of these studies if we do not have the raw data. The first solution to this problem, by averaging zeta-scores, has been attributed to Samuel A. Stouffer. In particular, it has been noted (2) that this method was introduced in footnote number 15 of the 1949 *The American Soldier*, a ponderous analysis of socio-psychological data collected by the USA War Department, during World War II (3). Therefore, to introduce this method, I will use the original data from the paper, collected in Table 1. The null hypothesis for each comparison is that there is no difference between soldiers in camps with WACs and those from camps without WACs. While it is not specified in the reference how the statistical test was conducted, we can consider the framework commonly used for statistical testing in Relative Risk assessment. In our case, we write

$$\text{Eq. 1} \quad RR_{1,0} = \frac{P(Y=1, X=1)}{P(Y=1, X=0)}$$

Where Y is a binary variable that assumes the value of one when a soldier responds NO to the following question: *If you had a sister, 21 years or older, would you like to see her join the WAC or not?* Moreover, X is a binary variable that is zero when the soldier belongs to a camp without WAC, while its value is 1 if the camp has WAC. It is possible to show (4) that under the null hypothesis, we have

$$\text{Eq. 2} \quad Z = \frac{\ln RR_{1,0}}{\sqrt{\frac{1-p_1}{p_1 n_1} + \frac{1-p_0}{p_0 n_0}}} \sim N(0,1)$$

Where p_1 is $P(Y = 1, X = 1)$ and $p_0 = P(Y = 1, X = 0)$, with n_0 and n_1 the size of the two samples under comparison. Therefore, we can test the null hypothesis by calculating the following two-sided p-values:

$$\text{Eq. 3} \quad p = 2\Phi(-|Z|)$$

In Table 1, I use Eq. 2 and Eq. 3 to perform Z and p-value calculations, including the standard error of the logarithm of the risk ratio:

$$\text{Eq. 4} \quad SE = \sqrt{\frac{1-p_1}{p_1 n_1} + \frac{1-p_0}{p_0 n_0}}$$

Education	Soldiers from camps with WACs	Soldiers from camps without WACs	RR	lnRR	SE	Z	p val
High-school graduate	53% (315)	49% (1,376)	1.082	0.079	0.06	1.317	1.88E-01
Some High-school	42% (215)	40% (864)	1.05	0.049	0.09	0.544	5.86E-01
Grade-school only	34% (262)	28% (1,234)	1.214	0.194	0.097	2	4.55E-02

Table 1. Two groups of soldiers were asked the same question: “If you had a sister, 21 years or older, would you like to see her join the WAC or not?”. WAC stands for Women’s Army Corps. Male soldiers came from both camps with WACs and camps without WACs. They were stratified by level of education. The percentages refer to those soldiers who would be disapproving of their sisters joining the WACs. We see that the higher the education level, the more the disapproval; also, soldiers in camps with WACs tended to be more frequently against WACs. The sample size for each group is indicated within brackets.

That said, in the original paper, the authors suggest summing the “relevant ratios” and dividing by $\sqrt{3}$ to obtain a new ratio that could be representative of all three educational groups. They also mention that this new value is 2.17 and that it reaches significance at 5%. If we follow this recipe using our Z-scores, we have:

$$Z_{meta} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^3 Z_i}{\sqrt{3}} = 2.29 \Rightarrow p_{meta} = 2.5 \cdot 10^{-2}$$

This was the first appearance in the scientific literature of the so-called *Z-transform test*, which, for this reason, is generally attributed to Stouffer. The division by the number of studies used in the meta-analysis is justified by the requirement for Z_{meta} to have – under the null hypothesis – a standard normal distribution. In the example above, under the null, $\sum_{i=1}^3 Z_i$ is the sum of three independent normal standard random variables; therefore, its variance is 3, and to normalise this random variable, we need to divide by $\sqrt{3}$, so that its variance is one. This means that, generally speaking, this method suggests using as Z-score of r independent studies, the value

$$\text{Eq. 5} \quad Z_{meta} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^r Z_i}{\sqrt{r}}$$

Where Z_i is the zeta score of the i^{th} study. From Z_{meta} , the overall p-value can be calculated as $p = 2\Phi(-|Z_{meta}|)$. Notably, in the case of one-tailed tests, where a small p-value indicates a negative Z and a p-value greater than 0.5 corresponds to a positive Z, we can formulate this test without the need for Z-scores, as follows

$$\text{Eq. 6} \quad p_{meta} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^r \Phi^{-1}(p_i)}{\sqrt{r}}$$

if Φ^{-1} includes the lower tail. The calculations of this paragraph have been carried out by the following R script.

```

# name: Z_transform.R
#
# This script runs the analysis from footnote 15 (page 44) of 1949
# sociological study "The American Soldier" by Stouffer
# https://archive.org/details/americansoldier20000samu
#
# Data
#
mydata<-data.frame(education=c("High_School","Some_High_School","Grad_School","Meta"),
                    WAC_f=c(0.53,0.42,0.34,NA),WAC_n=c(315,215,262,NA),
                    NOWAC_f=c(0.49,0.4,0.28,NA),NOWAC_n=c(1376,864,1234,NA))#
# Risk Ratios
#
for (i in 1:3) {
#
# Risk Ratios and logRRs
#
mydata$RR[i]<-round(mydata$WAC_f[i]/mydata$NOWAC_f[i],3)
mydata$lnRR[i]<-round(log(mydata$RR[i]),3)
#
# Standard errors
#
p1<-mydata$WAC_f[i]
p0<-mydata$NOWAC_f[i]
n1<-mydata$WAC_n[i]
n0<-mydata$NOWAC_n[i]
mydata$SE[i]<-round(sqrt((1-p1)/(n1*p1)+(1-p0)/(n0*p0)),3)
#
# Z scores
#
mydata$Z[i]<-round(mydata$lnRR[i]/mydata$SE[i],3)
#
# p values (two-sided)
#
mydata$p_val[i]<-format(2*pnorm(-abs(mydata$Z[i])),scientific=T,digits=3)
}
#
# Meta-analysis by Z-transform test
#
Z_meta<-round(sum(mydata$Z[1:3])/sqrt(3),3)
print(Z_meta)
p_val_meta<-format(2*pnorm(-abs(Z_meta)),scientific=T,digits=3)
print(p_val_meta)
#
# Save table
#
write.csv(mydata,"Z_transform.csv",quote=F,row.names=F)

```

3 Weighted Z-method

The Z-transform test is a particular case of a more general test published in 1958 by Liptak (5) who proposes in equation 6.3 the following expression for the one-tailed p-value of the meta-analysis:

$$\text{Eq. 7} \quad p_{meta} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^r w_i \Phi^{-1}(p_i)}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^r w_i^2}}$$

When the weights w_i are all assumed equal to one, we have the Z-transform test (Eq. 6). More generally, Liptak states that they “*should be chosen proportional to the expected difference between the null-hypothesis and the real situation and inversely proportional to the standard deviation of the statistics used for testing in the i^{th} experiment ($i = 1, 2, \dots, r$)*”. Also, the author suggests that: “*Generally, the standard deviation is inversely proportional to the square root of the number of observations of this experiment. If there is no information available but the number n_i of observations in the experiments ($i = 1, 2, \dots, r$) the weights may be chosen proportional to the square roots of these numbers.*” The translation of Eq. 7 is written as follows:

$$\text{Eq. 8} \quad Z_{meta} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^r w_i Z_i}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^r w_i^2}}, \quad w_i = \sqrt{n_i}$$

Where n_i is the size of i^{th} experiment. In the case of a two-tailed test, the p-value of the meta-analysis is calculated as $p = 2\Phi(-|Z_{meta}|)$. Notably, Z_{meta} in Eq. 8 follows a standard normal distribution under H_0 , as it is easily verifiable.

4 Meta-analysis of independent GWASs

In a genome-wide association study (GWAS), the regressions between the phenotype and the genotype are carried out according to either a logistic or a linear mixed model. In both cases, a Z-score is available for each genomic position included in the study. This means that different GWASs can be meta-analysed by means of the weighted Z-method, no matter the regression model employed in the original GWASs (1).

Phenotype	$X = 0$	$X = 1$	$X = 2$	Number of subjects
$Y = 1$	S_0	S_1	S_2	n_D
$Y = 0$	R_0	R_1	R_2	n_H
	n_0	n_1	$N - n_0 - n_1$	N

Table 2. In a GWAS for a binary trait, the phenotype is represented by a binary variable Y and the genotype is represented by a three-level variable X , where zero indicates homozygosity for the reference allele, 1 indicates heterozygosity, and 2 is the genotype corresponding to homozygosity for the alternative allele. N : sample size. n_D : number of cases. n_H : number of controls. n_0 : number of subjects homozygous for the reference allele. n_1 : number of heterozygous subjects.

4.1 Logistic regression for binary traits

To provide some context (the reader may skip this paragraph), let us consider the case of a GWAS involving a disease, modelled as a binary phenotype (either you have the disease, or you are healthy), and employing logistic regression. For each variant genotyped, we can build a table like Table 2, where S_0 is the number of individuals who have the disease ($Y = 1$) and who have two reference alleles ($X = 0$), S_1 is the number of individuals who have the disease and have one reference allele and one alternative allele, and so on. In other words, for each subject, the dependent variable Y indicates the disease status, while the explanatory variable X indicates the genotype. The relationship between the independent variable and the explanatory one, in GWAS studies, is set as

$$\text{Eq. 9} \quad \log \left(\frac{P(Y=1|X=x)}{P(Y=0|X=x)} \right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x, \quad x = 0, 1, 2$$

For $x = 0$ this model gives

$$\text{Eq. 10} \quad \beta_0 = \log \left(\frac{P(Y=1|X=0)}{P(Y=0|X=0)} \right) = \log \left(\frac{S_0}{R_0} \right)$$

Thus, for $x = 1$ we get

$$\text{Eq. 11} \quad \beta_1 = \log \left(\frac{P(Y=1|X=1)/P(Y=1|X=0)}{P(Y=0|X=1)/P(Y=0|X=0)} \right) = \log \left(\frac{S_1 R_0}{R_1 S_0} \right)$$

In other words, β_1 is the logarithm of the ratio between the odds of having the disease with genotype $X = 1$ and the odds of having the disease with the genotype $X = 0$. For $x = 2$ we can also write

$$\begin{aligned} & \log \left(\frac{P(Y = 1|X = 2)}{P(Y = 0|X = 2)} \right) = \beta_0 + 2\beta_1 = \\ & = \log \left(\frac{P(Y = 1|X = 0)}{P(Y = 0|X = 0)} \right) + \log \left(\frac{P(Y = 1|X = 1)/P(Y = 1|X = 0)}{P(Y = 0|X = 1)/P(Y = 0|X = 0)} \right)^2 \Rightarrow \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Eq. 12} \quad OR_{2,0} = \frac{P(Y=1|X=2)/P(Y=1|X=0)}{P(Y=0|X=2)/P(Y=0|X=0)} = \left(\frac{P(Y=1|X=1)/P(Y=1|X=0)}{P(Y=0|X=1)/P(Y=0|X=0)} \right)^2 = OR_{1,0}^2$$

So the odds ratio relative to the genotype $X = 2$ is the second power of the odds ratio for the genotype $X = 1$. The null hypothesis is assumed to be the equality between the odds of having the disease under the genotypes $X = 1$ and $X = 0$:

$$\text{Eq. 13} \quad H_0: \frac{P(Y=1|X=1)/P(Y=1|X=0)}{P(Y=0|X=1)/P(Y=0|X=0)} = 1 \Leftrightarrow \beta_1 = 0$$

It can be shown that under H_0 it is approximately

$$\text{Eq. 14} \quad \beta_1 \sim N \left(\mu = 0, \sigma^2 = \frac{1}{n_0 p(1-p)} + \frac{1}{n_1 p(1-p)} \right)$$

Where $p = P(Y = 1|X = 1) = P(Y = 1|X = 0)$ and $n_0 = S_0 + R_0, n_1 = S_1 + R_1$. The statistical test for the regression of Eq. 9 is therefore

$$\text{Eq. 15} \quad p = 2\Phi(-|Z|), \quad Z = \frac{\hat{\beta}_1}{SE(\hat{\beta}_1)}$$

Where $SE(\hat{\beta}_1)$ is the standard error of the regression coefficient, which comes from the method of maximum likelihood (see par. 13 of (6)) and it is given by

$$SE(\hat{\beta}_1) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N p_i(1-p_i)x_i^2}}, \quad p_i = P(Y = 1|X = x_i)$$

We want to simplify this formula by considering a mean value for p_i and we note that

$$P(Y = 1|X = 0) = \frac{S_0}{S_0 + R_0}, P(Y = 1|X = 1) = \frac{S_1}{S_1 + R_1}, P(Y = 1|X = 2) = \frac{S_2}{S_2 + R_2}$$

A ponderate mean of these three values, using the weights $\frac{S_0+R_0}{N}$, $\frac{S_1+R_1}{N}$, $\frac{S_2+R_2}{N}$ respectively, we have $p_i \cong \frac{S_0+S_1+S_2}{N}$, which is the proportion of cases:

$$\text{Eq. 16} \quad \phi \triangleq \frac{S_0+S_1+S_2}{N}$$

Then $\sum_{i=1}^N p_i(1-p_i)x_i^2 = \phi(1-\phi)\sum_{i=1}^N x_i^2$. We now consider the discrete random variable X and we have

$$E[X^2] = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N x_i^2}{N} = 2 \frac{0(S_0 + R_0) + 1(S_1 + R_1) + 4(S_2 + R_2)}{2N} = 2f + 2 \frac{2(S_2 + R_2)}{2N} = 2f + 2f^2$$

where $f = \frac{S_1+R_1+2(S_2+R_2)}{2N}$ is the minor allele frequency, and we have considered that under the Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium, the probability of minor allele homozygosity is $\frac{2(S_2+R_2)}{2N} = f^2$. Since $E[X] = 2f$ and in reality, we use a centred value for X , with an abuse of notation, we have

$$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N x_i^2}{N} = 2f + 2f^2 - 4f^2 = 2f(1-f)$$

That said, we have found for the standard error the expression

$$\text{Eq. 17} \quad SE(\hat{\beta}_1) \cong \frac{1}{\sqrt{2Nf(1-f)\phi(1-\phi)}}, \quad \phi = \frac{S_0+S_1+S_2}{N}, f = \frac{S_1+R_1+2(S_2+R_2)}{2N}$$

As a reference for these formulae, see (7, 8). For a rigorous derivation, see chapter 13 of (9).

4.2 Weighted Z-method for GWAS meta-analysis

Genome-wide studies calculate regression coefficients from either logistic or linear regression; therefore, they are not directly comparable, and the scale for transforming one into the other is not easily calculated (10). On the other hand, Z-scores from the two regression models are directly comparable, since they always follow a standard normal distribution under the null hypothesis of no differences in genotype between patients and controls. We can therefore use a weighted Z-method for meta-analysis of GWAS with independent samples, by direct application of Eq. 8. It has been suggested to use, for studies with unequal numbers of cases and controls, the effective sample size N_{eff} instead of the actual one, to calculate the weights:

$$\text{Eq. 18} \quad Z_{meta} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^r w_i Z_i}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^r w_i^2}}, \quad w_i = \sqrt{N_{eff}^{(i)}}$$

with $N_{eff}^{(i)} \triangleq 4 \frac{n_D^{(i)} n_H^{(i)}}{N^{(i)}}$, where $n_D^{(i)}, n_H^{(i)}, N^{(i)}$ are the number of cases, the number of controls, and the sample size of study i , respectively. Note that when $n_D = n_H = \frac{N}{2}$, we have $N_{eff} = 4 \frac{N^2}{4N} = N$. To calculate the overall p-value from Z_{meta} we apply

$$\text{Eq. 19} \quad p_{meta} = 2\Phi(-|Z_{meta}|)$$

We can then calculate the standard error by using Eq. 17:

$$\text{Eq. 20} \quad SE_{meta}(\hat{\beta}_1) \cong \frac{1}{\sqrt{2N_{meta}f_{meta}(1-f_{meta})\phi_{meta}(1-\phi_{meta})}}$$

where $\phi_{meta} = \frac{\sum_1^r n_D^{(i)}}{\sum_1^r N^{(i)}}$, $f = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^r f_i N^{(i)}}{N_{meta}}$, $N_{meta} = \sum_{i=1}^r N^{(i)}$.

4.3 Simulated meta-analysis

We now consider two GWASs for a binary trait of a single variant. Assuming that the trait is the same in both GWASs and that the variant is the same, we want to compare the results of the meta-analysis by the weighted-Z method and the statistical analysis from pooling subject-level data. In the first two rows of Table 3 we have the results of the logistic regressions performed according to what was described in par. 4.1 for two case-control populations, one of 87k subjects and the other of 83k participants, generated by random extraction of the genotypes from a pool of 100 alleles (either 0 or 1, with the latter the effect allele). These 100 alleles included 43 effect alleles for the cases and 40 effect alleles for the controls in both the GWASs. The two populations were pooled for GWAS-3 (4th row of the table), and a meta-analysis (GWAS-Meta) was performed for GWAS-1 and GWAS-2 according to what was presented in par. 4.2.

	N_CAS	N_CON	N	Neff	FRQ	Beta	SE	Z	p_val
GWAS_1	7000	80000	87000	25747.13	0.402598	0.149843	0.017844	8.397362	4.57E-17
GWAS_2	3000	80000	83000	11566.27	0.400982	0.121071	0.026562	4.558084	5.16E-06
GWAS_meta	10000	160000	170000	37647.06	0.401809	0.141432	0.014867	9.513229	1.85E-21
GWAS_pooled	10000	160000	170000	37647.06	0.401809	0.140816	0.014735	9.556787	1.21E-21

Table 3. The first two rows contain the metadata of two GWASs built by random extraction, for each subject, of the genotype, setting a MAF in cases of 0.43 and a MAF in controls of 0.40. The third row includes the meta-analysis performed according to Eq. 18, Eq. 19, Eq. 20. Then, the last row shows the metadata of the regression performed by pooling the cases and the controls from GWAS-1 and GWAS-2.

The script used to calculate Table 3:

```
# name: weighted_Z_GWAS.R
#
# This script runs the weighted Z method to simulate GWASs
#
#-----
# This function builds a GWAS for a single variant and performs logistic regression
#-----
#
```

```

myGWAS<-function(n_D,n_H,MAF_cases,MAF_controls) {
#
# Build cases and controls
#
N<-n_D+n_H # sample size
mydata<-data.frame(Y=rep(NA,N),A1=rep(NA,N),A2=rep(NA,N),X=rep(NA,N))
#
# Build cases
#
MAF<-MAF_cases # allele frequency of effect allele (1)
alleles<-c(rep(1,MAF*100),rep(0,(1-MAF)*100)) # allelic pool in cases
for (i in 1:n_D) {
  mydata$Y[i]<-1
  mydata$A1[i]<-sample(alleles,1)
  mydata$A2[i]<-sample(alleles,1)
  mydata$X[i]<-mydata$A1[i]+mydata$A2[i]
}
#
# Build controls
#
MAF<-MAF_controls # allele frequency of effect allele (1)
alleles<-c(rep(1,MAF*100),rep(0,(1-MAF)*100)) # allelic pool in cases
for (i in (n_D+1):N) {
  mydata$Y[i]<-0
  mydata$A1[i]<-sample(alleles,1)
  mydata$A2[i]<-sample(alleles,1)
  mydata$X[i]<-mydata$A1[i]+mydata$A2[i]
}
#
# Perform logistic regression
#
model<-glm(Y~X,family=binomial,data=mydata)
Beta_1<-summary(model)$coefficients[2,1]
SE<-summary(model)$coefficients[2,2]
Zeta<-summary(model)$coefficients[2,3]
p_value<-summary(model)$coefficients[2,4]
#
# Results
#
myresult<-list("FRQ" = sum(mydata$X)/(2*N),
              "Beta" = Beta_1,
              "SE" = SE,
              "Z" = Zeta,
              "p_val" = p_value,
              "myGWAS" = mydata)
return(myresult)
}
#
#-----
# Prepare a data frame for two GWASs (single variant), meta-analysis, and pooled GWAS
# with subject-level data
#-----
#

```

```

mymeta<-data.frame(GWAS=rep(NA,4),
  N_CAS=rep(NA,4),N_CON=rep(NA,4),N=rep(NA,4),Neff=rep(NA,4),
  FRQ=rep(NA,4),Beta=rep(NA,4),SE=rep(NA,4),Z=rep(NA,4),p_val=rep(NA,4))
#
myList<-list() # we'll store the two GWASs we want to meta-analyse
set.seed(123) # results are reproducible
#
#-----
# Set MAF in cases and controls
#-----
#
MAF_CAS<-0.43 # frequency of effect allele in cases
MAF_CON<-0.40 # frequency of effect allele in controls
#
#-----
# GWAS-1
#-----
#
# Assign data
#
i<-1
#
mymeta$GWAS[i]<-paste0("GWAS_",i) # name
mymeta$N_CAS[i]<-7000 # number of cases
mymeta$N_CON[i]<-80000 # number of controls
mymeta$N[i]<-mymeta$N_CAS[i]+mymeta$N_CON[i]
mymeta$Neff[i]<-4*mymeta$N_CAS[i]*mymeta$N_CON[i]/mymeta$N[i] # effective size
#
myresult<-myGWAS(n_D=mymeta$N_CAS[i],n_H=mymeta$N_CON[i],
  MAF_cases=MAF_CAS,MAF_controls=MAF_CON)
#
# Save results
#
mymeta$FRQ[i]<-sum(myresult$myGWAS$X)/(2*mymeta$N[i])
mymeta$Beta[i]<-myresult$Beta
mymeta$SE[i]<-myresult$SE
mymeta$Z[i]<-myresult$Z
mymeta$p_val[i]<-myresult$p_val
#
myList[[i]]<-myresult$myGWAS
#
#-----
# GWAS-2
#-----
#
# Assign data
#
i<-2
#
mymeta$GWAS[i]<-paste0("GWAS_",i) # name
mymeta$N_CAS[i]<-3000 # number of cases
mymeta$N_CON[i]<-80000 # number of controls
mymeta$N[i]<-mymeta$N_CAS[i]+mymeta$N_CON[i]

```

```

mymeta$Neff[i]<-4*mymeta$N_CAS[i]*mymeta$N_CON[i]/mymeta$N[i] # effective size
#
myresult<-myGWAS(n_D=mymeta$N_CAS[i],n_H=mymeta$N_CON[i],
  MAF_cases=MAF_CAS,MAF_controls=MAF_CON)
#
# Save results
#
mymeta$FRQ[i]<-sum(myresult$myGWAS$X)/(2*mymeta$N[i])
mymeta$Beta[i]<-myresult$Beta
mymeta$SE[i]<-myresult$SE
mymeta$Z[i]<-myresult$Z
mymeta$p_val[i]<-myresult$p_val
#
myList[[i]]<-myresult$myGWAS
#
#-----
# Meta Analysis
#-----
#
i<-3
#
mymeta$GWAS[i]<-"GWAS_meta"
mymeta$N_CAS[i]<-mymeta$N_CAS[1]+mymeta$N_CAS[2]
mymeta$N_CON[i]<-mymeta$N_CON[1]+mymeta$N_CON[2]
mymeta$N[i]<-mymeta$N[1]+mymeta$N[2]
mymeta$Neff[i]<-4*mymeta$N_CAS[i]*mymeta$N_CON[i]/mymeta$N[i]
mymeta$FRQ[i]<-sum(mymeta$FRQ[1:2]*mymeta$N[1:2])/mymeta$N[i]
#
# Calculate Z_meta
#
w<-sqrt(mymeta$Neff[1:2]) # weights
mymeta$Z[i]<-sum(mymeta$Z[1:2]*w)/sqrt(sum(w^2))
mymeta$p_val[i]<-2*pnorm(-abs(mymeta$Z[i]))
#
# Calculate SE and Beta
#
phi<-mymeta$N_CAS[i]/mymeta$N[i]
mymeta$SE[i]<-(2*mymeta$N[i]*mymeta$FRQ[i]*(1-mymeta$FRQ[i])*phi*(1-phi))^-0.5
mymeta$Beta[i]<-mymeta$SE[i]*mymeta$Z[i]
#
#-----
# Pooled GWAS
#-----
#
i<-4
#
mymeta$GWAS[i]<-"GWAS_pooled"
mymeta$N_CAS[i]<-mymeta$N_CAS[1]+mymeta$N_CAS[2]
mymeta$N_CON[i]<-mymeta$N_CON[1]+mymeta$N_CON[2]
mymeta$N[i]<-mymeta$N[1]+mymeta$N[2]
mymeta$Neff[i]<-4*mymeta$N_CAS[i]*mymeta$N_CON[i]/mymeta$N[i]
mymeta$FRQ[i]<-sum(mymeta$FRQ[1:2]*mymeta$N[1:2])/mymeta$N[i]
#

```

```

mydata<-rbind(myList[[1]],myList[[2]])
#
# Perform logistic regression
#
model<-glm(Y~X,family=binomial,data=mydata)
#
# Results
#
mymeta$Beta[i]<-summary(model)$coefficients[2,1]
mymeta$SE[i]<-summary(model)$coefficients[2,2]
mymeta$Z[i]<-summary(model)$coefficients[2,3]
mymeta$p_val[i]<-summary(model)$coefficients[2,4]
#
#-----
# Write results
#-----
#
write.csv(mymeta,"Meta_GWAS.csv",row.names=F)

```

5 Meta-analysis of GWASs with overlapping samples

In the weighted Z -method, it is assumed that the cohorts are independent, which translates into independence between the Z scores from the different experiments. This is no longer true when we meta-analyze two GWASs with a partial overlap in subjects, the extent of which may even be unknown.

To deal with this situation, we note that, in the case of independent studies, and under H_0 (no association between the phenotype and the genotype), Z scores of the r GWASs we want to perform a meta-analysis on must define a random vector of independent normal standard random variables. On the other hand, if an overlap between samples is present, these variables are not independent anymore, and their covariance matrix has non-zero elements outside the main diagonal. That said, we can calculate a correction for the zeta scores by calculating the change of variables that must be operated for the Z scores to be independent.

To fix our ideas, let us consider two GWASs only – $GWAS_1$ and $GWAS_2$ – with overlapping samples. Let also be $\mathbf{Z} = [\mathbf{Z}_1, \mathbf{Z}_2]$ the random vector whose components are the vector of Z scores of $GWAS_1$ and of $GWAS_2$, respectively. The joint probability distribution is:

$$f_{\mathbf{Z}}(z_1, z_2) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{|C|}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}[z_1 \ z_2]C^{-1}\begin{bmatrix} z_1 \\ z_2 \end{bmatrix}}$$

Where

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \rho_{1,2} \\ \rho_{1,2} & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad |C| = 1 - \rho_{1,2}^2$$

We know from algebra that, since C is a symmetric matrix, it can be diagonalised. In particular, it is possible to find an orthogonal matrix P such that

$$[z_1 \quad z_2]C^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} z_1 \\ z_2 \end{bmatrix} = [z_1 \quad z_2]P \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\lambda_1} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{\lambda_2} \end{bmatrix} P^T \begin{bmatrix} z_1 \\ z_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

Where λ_1, λ_2 are the eigenvalues of C. The columns of P are the corresponding eigenvectors of C. This also means that the transformation

$$\begin{bmatrix} \zeta_1 \\ \zeta_2 \end{bmatrix} = P^T \begin{bmatrix} z_1 \\ z_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

defines a new random vector whose components are Gaussian independent random variables. They are not standard, though, but we can standardise them by normalization:

$$z'_1 = \frac{\zeta_1}{\lambda_1}, z'_2 = \frac{\zeta_2}{\lambda_2}$$

More generally, for a number r of GWASs, we define a transformation of variables for the zeta scores that can be written as follows:

$$\text{Eq. 21} \quad \begin{bmatrix} z'_1(j) \\ z'_2(j) \\ \vdots \\ z'_r(j) \end{bmatrix} = \left(P^T \begin{bmatrix} z_1(j) \\ z_2(j) \\ \vdots \\ z_r(j) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\lambda_1} & \frac{1}{\lambda_2} & \dots & \frac{1}{\lambda_r} \end{bmatrix} \right)^T = \begin{bmatrix} 1/\lambda_1 \\ 1/\lambda_2 \\ \vdots \\ 1/\lambda_r \end{bmatrix} [z_1^{(j)} \quad z_2^{(j)} \quad \dots \quad z_r^{(j)}]P$$

for j that indicates the position of the SNP and where P is the matrix whose column are the eigenvector of C (the correlation matrix of $\mathbf{Z} = [\mathbf{Z}_1, \mathbf{Z}_2, \dots, \mathbf{Z}_r]$) and $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_r$ are the corresponding eigenvalues. Once we have calculated the corrected Zs, we can calculate Z_{meta} by direct application of Eq. 18.

It may be advisable to remove the SNPs where at least one GWAS has a Z above 1 (in module) before the calculation of the correction, because at these position the null hypothesis of no regression between the genotype and the phenotype is less likely. Once the correction has been calculated (once we have P and $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_r$) it must be applied to all the Zs, included those that have a module above 1. A method similar to the one here discussed, can be found in (11).

6 References

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